

EVALUATION OF A COMPREHENSIVE VAJIKARANA REGIMEN IN KLAIBYA: AN
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ABSTRACT

Background: Erectile Dysfunction (ED), defined as the persistent inability to achieve or maintain an erection for satisfactory sexual activity, is a major global concern projected to affect over 320 million men by 2025. Ayurveda describes ED as *Klaibya*, primarily associated with *Vata* vitiation and *Shukra dhatu kshaya*. *Vajikarana* therapy offers a holistic, multi-modal approach to its management. **Objectives** is to evaluate the efficacy of a combined *Vajikarana* protocol comprising *Guduchyamalakadi Kashaya* for *Ama pachana*, *Payasa Eranda Taila Kostashodhana*, *Ksheera Vaitarana Basti*, *Vidarikanda Taila Uttarabasti*, *Manmathabhra Rasa*, and *Shishna Lepa* in the management of *Klaibya*. To assess the efficacy of *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati* with *Shishna Lepa*. To compare both modalities for relative therapeutic effectiveness. **Methods:** An open-labelled randomized controlled trial was conducted for 36 days on two groups. Group A received the comprehensive *Vajikarana* regimen, while Group B received *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati* with *Shishna Lepa*. Subjective and objective outcomes were assessed before and after treatment and analysed using contingency tables. **Results:** Group A demonstrated highly significant improvement in all subjective parameters ($P < 0.0001$) compared to Group B. In hormonal markers, total testosterone improved markedly in Group A ($P < 0.0001$). Free testosterone and LH showed marginally better improvement in Group B. FSH showed a non-significant trend toward improvement in Group A. Prolactin and TSH remained unchanged in both groups. **Conclusion:** The comprehensive *Vajikarana* protocol provided significantly superior improvement in psychosexual and physiological parameters of ED compared to the limited regimen. Multi-modal Ayurvedic interventions therefore offer enhanced therapeutic benefit in the management of *Klaibya*.

KEYWORDS: Erectile Dysfunction, Klaibya, Vajikarana, Vidarikanda, Uttarabasti, Manmathabhra Rasa.

INTRODUCTION

Sexual health is a fundamental component of human well-being, contributing not only to reproductive capability but also to emotional intimacy, psychological stability, and overall quality of life. Ayurveda considers healthy sexual activity, practiced within balance and ethical conduct, as an important factor in nourishing *Ojas* the essence responsible for vitality, immunity, and strength. Preservation of sexual health is therefore

integral to achieving the *Purusharthas*, particularly *Kama* (pleasure) and *Sukha* (happiness).

Erectile Dysfunction^[1] (ED), or impotence, is one of the most prevalent male sexual health disorders worldwide. It is defined as the persistent inability to achieve or maintain an erection adequate for satisfactory sexual performance. While transient episodes of difficulty are common, chronic ED poses a significant global burden, affecting approximately 15–30% of men, with

prevalence increasing substantially after the age of 40.^[2] In India, lifestyle changes, urban stress, diabetes, hypertension, obesity, and other metabolic disorders have contributed to a noticeable rise in ED, yet social stigma continues to limit open discussions and early treatment-seeking. Conventional medical management including PDE5 inhibitors such as sildenafil offers symptomatic relief but often fails to address the multifactorial aetiology of ED. Adverse effects, psychological contributors, dependence, and limited long-term efficacy highlight the need for more holistic and sustainable therapeutic approaches. Surgical and mechanical interventions, though effective in select cases, are invasive and may not be acceptable to all patients.

Ayurveda classifies ED under *Klaibya*^[3], attributing its pathogenesis to *Shukra Dhatu kshaya* and *Vata* vitiation. Its management emphasizes *Vajikarana*, an Ayurvedic specialty dedicated to enhancing reproductive vitality, promoting mental well-being, and restoring the integrity of *Shukra Dhatu*. This includes *Rasayana & Vajikarna* therapy, *Vrsya* herbs such as *Vidarikanda*, *Ashwagandha*, *Shatavari*, *Kapikacchu*, and *Gokshura* etc as well as herbo-mineral preparations like *Manmathabhra Rasa* and *Makaradhwaja Vati* etc. Panchakarma procedures particularly *Basti & Uttarabasti* therapies are highlighted for their ability to correct *Vata* imbalance, improve penile tissue nourishment, and enhance erectile function.

Given the increasing burden of ED and the limitations of contemporary treatments, there is a growing need to evaluate integrative Ayurvedic interventions that address both the physiological and psychological dimensions of the disorder. The present study investigates a comprehensive *Vajikarana* protocol incorporating *Uttarabasti*, *Kostashodhana*, *Ama Pachana*, oral *Vajikarana* formulations, and *Shishna Lepa*, in comparison with a simplified OPD-friendly regimen, to determine their relative efficacy in the management of *Klaibya*.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES AIM

To explore the Ayurvedic interpretation of Erectile Dysfunction.

To evaluate and compare the combined *Vajikarana* effect of *Guduchyamalakadi kashaya Pachana*, *Koṣṭhashodhana* with *Payasa Eranda Taila*, *Vidarikanda Taila Uttarabasti* and *Manmathabhra Rasa*, *Shishna Lepa* with that of *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati* and *Shishna Lepa* alone in the management of *Klaibya* (Erectile Dysfunction).

OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the combined *Vajikarana* effect of *Guduchyamalakadi kashaya Pachana*, *Koṣṭhashodhana* with *Payasa Eranda Taila*, *Vidarikanda Taila Uttarabasti* and *Manmathabhra Rasa*, *Shishna Lepa* in the management of *klaibya*(ED).

- To evaluate the efficacy of only oral *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati* and *Shishna Lepa* in the management of *klaibya* (ED).
- To compare the effect of *Guduchyamalakadi kashaya Pachana*, *Koṣṭhashodhana* with *Payasa Eranda Taila*, *Vidarikanda Taila Uttarabasti* and *Manmathabhra Rasa*, *Shishna Lepa* over only *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati* and *Shishna Lepa* in erectile dysfunction(*klaibya*)”

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

Prospective, Controlled Comparative open-label RCT study where 40 patients of Erectile Dysfunction were randomly selected and assigned into two groups consisting of 20 patients in each. Group A patients were subjected to *guduchyamalakadi kashaya pachana*, *kostashodhana* with *payasa eranda taila*, *vidarikanda taila uttarabasti* and *manmathabhra rasa*, *shishna lepa* for 36 days, and Group B received only *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati & Shishna Lepa*.

Source of patients

40 Patients of *Klaibya* (ED) will be randomly selected (irrespective of caste) from OPD and IPD of Taranath government ayurvedic medical college and hospital Bellary.

CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF CASES

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Male Subjects aged between 21 to 55 years
- Male Subjects having classical *lakshanas of klaibya*, erectile dysfunction like

Linga saithilya

Mlana sishnuta

Mogha Sankalpachesta

Dhvajanuccharya

Swasartha

Svinnagatrata

- Subjects willing to participate in the study and ready to sign informed consent form.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Subjects presented with HIV and STD's, Prolapsed rectum, Lacerated ano-rectum, urethral stricture and any critical emergencies.
- Subject unfit for *Niruha basti* and *Uttara basti*.\

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

a) Subjective parameters

Subjects will be diagnosed based on the classical sign and symptoms of *klaibya*^[4] (ED) =

Linga shaithilya- flaccid penis

Mlana sishnuta- Constricted penis

Mogha Sankalpachesta- Futile sexual activity

Dhvajanuccharya- Lack of erection

Swasartha- Breathlessness during intercourse

Svinnagatrata- Profuse sweating during intercourse

b) objective parameters

- Sr FSH
- Sr LH
- Sr TSH
- Sr PROLACTIN
- Sr TESTOSTERON (FREE AND TOTAL)

INTERVENTION**GROUP A - 20 PATIENT****Table no. 1: showing Intervention.**

PROCEDURE	YOGA	DOSAGE	DURATION	SEVANA KALA	SAHAPANA
DEEPANA PACHANA, (<i>Guduchyamalakadi churna</i> ^[5])	<i>Musta</i> - 1 part <i>Guduchi</i> - 2 parts <i>Amalaki</i> - 4 parts	3gm	5 DAYS (Day 1-Day 5)	TID Before food	<i>Musta, Guduchi, Amalaki Kashaya</i>
KOSTHA SHODHANA	<i>Eranda Taila</i> ^[6]	50ml	01 Day (Day 6)	Early Morning Empty stomach	Hot Milk 100 ml
BASTI (As a <i>PurvaKarma for Uttarabasti</i>)	<i>Vaitarana basti</i> ^[7] <i>Saindhava lavana</i> - 15gms <i>Amlika</i> - 50ml <i>Guda</i> - 25gms <i>Taila-Vidarikanda taila</i> -50ml <i>gopayas</i> - 200ml milk	340 ml	3 days (Day 7-Day 9)	Morning, Empty stomach	
UTTARABASTI ^[8]	<i>Vidarikanda</i> ^[9] <i>taila</i>	40ml	05 Days (Day 7-Day 11)		
VAJIKARANA YOGA	<i>Manmathabra Rasa</i> ^[10]	500 Mg vati	24 DAYS (12 th Day-36 th)	BD Before food	<i>Madhu & dugdha</i>
SHISHNA LEPA (external application)	<i>Vidarikanda taila</i>	Quantity sufficient	36 Days	Night before bed time	

GROUP B- 20 PATIENTS

PROCEDURE	YOGA	DOSAGE	DURATION	SEVANA KALA	SAHAPANA
VAJIKARANA YOGA	<i>Vidarikanda ghana vati</i>	500 Mg	36 DAYS	2 TID Before food	<i>Musta, Guduchi, Amalaki Kashaya</i>
SHISHNA LEPA (external application)	<i>Vidarikanda taila</i>	Quantity sufficient	36 DAYS	Night before bed time	

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

In group A maximum number i.e 17 (85%) patients had *Dhvajanucharya*, 12 (60%) patients had *Lingashaithilya*, 11 (55%) patients had *Mogasankalpachesta*, 10 (50%) patients had *Svinnagatrata*, 03(15%) patients had *Mukashosha* and 02(10%) patients had *Mlanashishnata*.

In group B maximum number i.e 15 (75%) patients had *Dhvajanucharya*, 14 (70%) patients had *Lingashaithilya*, 09 (45%) patients each had *Mogasankalpachesta* & *Svinnagatrata*, 03 (15%) patients had *Mlanashishnata* and 02(10%) patients had *Mukashosha*.

In group A among Eleven subjective parameters All showed statistically highly significant results. Among 6 objective parameters Free Testosterone & Total Testosterone showed statistically highly significant results. Serum FSH & LH showed statistically significant result, Prolactin & TSH showed statistically non-significant result.

In group B among Eleven subjective parameters All showed statistically highly significant results. Among 6 objective parameters Free Testosterone & Total Testosterone showed statistically highly significant results. LH showed statistically significant result, Serum FSH, Prolactin & TSH showed statistically non-significant result.

Table no. 2: showing comparison of group A and group B.

	Parameters	Group A P value	Group B P value	Better group
Subjective Parameter	<i>Lingashaithilya</i>	<0.0001	0.0001	Group A
	<i>Mlanashishnata</i>	<0.0001	0.0005	Group A
	<i>Mogasankalpachesta</i>	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	<i>Dhvajanuccharya</i>	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	<i>Svinnagatrata</i>	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	<i>Mukashosha</i>	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	Sexual Desire	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	Erection	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	Rigidity	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	Ejaculation	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	Performance Anxiety	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
Objective Parameter	Free Testosterone	0.0009	<0.0001	Group B
	Total Testosterone	<0.0001	<0.0001	Group A
	FSH	0.0821	0.2348	Group A
	LH	0.0289	0.0040	Group B
	Prolactin	0.8385	0.5741	Group B
	TSH	0.1906	0.0522	Group B

On comparison, Both Group A and Group B showed statistically highly significant improvement in all eleven subjective parameters. Among six objective parameters, Free and Total Testosterone showed statistically highly significant results in both groups. In Group A, Serum FSH and LH were statistically significant, while

Prolactin and TSH were non-significant. In Group B, only LH was statistically significant, with Serum FSH, Prolactin, and TSH showing non-significant changes. Overall, Group A exhibited a wider range of significant changes than Group B.

Graph no. 01 showing overall % of group A and group B.

DISCUSSION

Sexual health is a vital component of overall well-being, with significant physical, emotional, and social implications. In Ayurveda, it is recognized as one of the three pillars (*Upasthambhas*) essential for sustaining life, and *Vajikarana* is the specialized branch dedicated to enhancing sexual vitality and *Shukra Dhatu*. *Klaibya* (erectile dysfunction) is understood as a multifactorial disorder, arising from *Dhatukshaya*, *Manasika Bhavas*, and improper lifestyle, affecting both body and mind. Its growing prevalence in modern society linked to stress, metabolic disorders, and sedentary habits makes Ayurvedic approaches highly relevant. Studies show ED

affects a significant percentage of men in India and globally, with rising incidence in diabetics and older age groups. Ayurveda offers a holistic perspective that addresses not just symptoms but the root cause, promoting rejuvenation, vitality, and mental well-being through *Vajikarana Chikitsa*. Therefore, *Klaibya* is not merely a reproductive issue but a reflection of deeper systemic and lifestyle imbalances.

GUDUCHYAMALAKADI KASHAYA

Guduchyamalaki Yoga is mentioned in *Charaka Samhita jwara adhikara* while explaining *chikitsa of chaturtaka jwara*. This yoga contains *Musta, guduchi*

and *Amalaki* which is *Majja & shukra dhatu pachaka* for the purpose of *Deepana & pachana*. Its dhatu-level *pachana* effect supports metabolic correction and contributes to restoring the functional integrity of reproductive tissues.

VAITARANA BASTI

Vaitarana basti i.e. *Ksheera vaitarana* explained in *Bastikarmadhikara* in *vangasena Samhita* which is *Brimhana, Vatanulomana & Shukrashodhaka* helps in clearing *shukravaha srotas*. *Ksheera Vaitarana Basti*, having *Tikta, Amla rasa, and Kshira (milk) as the Anupana, has Vatashamana, Shukravardhaka, and Snigdha* properties, beneficial for rejuvenation of *Shukra Dhatu*. The *basti's Snigdha, Sukshma, and Vyavayi* properties help restore *Shukra Dhatu* and support *Apana Vata* regulation. The formulation's ingredients provide synergistic benefits: *Saindhava Lavana* ensures effective *Srotoshodhana* and enhances drug penetration, while *Chincha Paka* supports *Apana Vayu* regulation through its *Anulomana* effect. *Vidarikanda Taila* nourishes and rejuvenates reproductive tissues, countering *Dhatu Kshaya*, and *Ksheera* acts as a *Rasayana* that strengthens *Ojas* and promotes *Shukra Dhatu* formation. *Guda* further contributes to *Vatahara and Brimhana* properties. Together, these actions improve neurovascular nourishment, libido, and erectile function while correcting the underlying *Vata imbalance*.

VIDARIKANDA TAILA UTTARABASTI

Vidarikanda Taila Uttarabasti is effective in *Klaibya* due to its *Brimhana, Vr̥sya, and Vata–Pitta Shamana* actions. The *Madhura, Snigdha, and Sita* qualities of *Vidarikanda* directly nourish *Shukra Dhatu* and strengthen *Apana Vayu*. Administered through *Uttarabasti*, the *taila* acts directly on *Apana Vayu* and pelvic structures, with its lipophilic nature enhancing absorption through the urethral mucosa. This localized action improves circulation, neurovascular stimulation, and erectile response by influencing tissues such as the corpora cavernosa, prostate, and pelvic nerves. Bioactive compounds like tuberosin promote nitric oxide (NO) release, facilitating vasodilation and improved penile blood flow. While isoflavones and phytosterols support androgen activity and testosterone balance. These combined effects promote *Shukra* nourishment, better pelvic circulation, and hormonal stability, making *Vidarikanda Taila Uttarabasti* a targeted and effective therapy for *Klaibya*.

MANMATHABRA RASA

Manmathabhra Rasa is a potent *Vajikarana* formulation effective in *Klaibya* due to its strong *Vr̥sya, Balya, and Rasayana* actions. *Kajjali* acts as a *Yogavahi*, enhancing tissue penetration and overall efficacy. *Abhraka, Vanga, Loha, and Tamra Bhasma* collectively support *Shukra Dhatu* regeneration, improve testicular and circulatory function, and promote *Srotoshodhana*, thereby strengthening the neurovascular mechanisms essential for erection. The herbal constituents—such as

Kapikacchu, Shatavari, Kokilaksha, Bala, and Vriddhadaruka provide L-DOPA, saponins, and flavonoids that enhance dopamine, testosterone, and nitric oxide activity, improving libido and erectile strength. Aromatic agents like *Karpura, Jeeraka, Yavani, Lavanga, and Jatiphala* further aid *Agnideepana*, circulation, and reduction of psychogenic stress. Together, these Herbo-mineral components correct *Vata* imbalance, rejuvenate *Shukra Dhatu*, stabilize mental functions, and enhance neuro-hormonal responses, making *Manmathabhra Rasa* a comprehensive therapy for *Klaibya*.

VIDARIKANDA GHANA VATI

Vidarikanda Ghana Vati, a concentrated extract of *Pueraria tuberosa*, supports the management of *Klaibya* through its *Brimhana, Vr̥sya, and Rasayana* actions. With *Madhura rasa, Guru–Snigdha guna, Sita virya, and Madhura vipaka*, it effectively pacifies *Vata–Pitta* and nourishes *Shukravaha Srotas*, improving the quality and strength of *Shukra Dhatu*. As a *Ghana* preparation, it ensures enhanced bioavailability and sustained therapeutic activity. Modern pharmacology supports these actions through its bioactive components viz, tuberosin enhances nitric oxide release and penile vasodilation, while isoflavonoids like puerarin, daidzein, and genistein modulate androgen receptors, support testosterone synthesis, and improve libido. Compounds such as β -sitosterol and stigmasterol further contribute to hormonal and metabolic balance, supporting vascular health essential for erectile function. Collectively, these actions enhance neurovascular response, hormonal stability, and reproductive tissue nourishment, making *Vidarikanda Ghana Vati* a valuable oral *Vajikarana* formulation for erectile dysfunction.

VIDARIKANDA LEPA

Vidarikanda Taila Lepa, prepared with *Pueraria tuberosa*, supports the management of *Klaibya* through its *Vr̥sya and Brimhana* actions. External application over the genital region allows the lipid-based formulation to deliver bioactive components such as tuberosin, puerarin, daidzein, genistein, and sitosterol directly to the penile tissues. These compounds improve local microcirculation and enhance nitric oxide (NO) release, promoting vasodilation and better penile blood flow, essential for erection. The *Vr̥sya and Balya* properties help stimulate androgen activity and support libido. By pacifying aggravated *Vata and Pitta doshas*, the *lepa* improves nerve function, penile sensation, and overall reproductive vitality. Thus, *Vidarikanda Taila Lepa* restores erectile function through a combination of local vasodilatory, antioxidant, neuroendocrine, and dosha-balancing mechanisms.

CONCLUSION

Sexual health is integral to physical, emotional, and psychological well-being, and disturbances in erectile function profoundly affect confidence, interpersonal relationships, and quality of life. In Ayurveda, *Klaibya* is

understood as a manifestation of *Vata* aggravation and *Shukra Dhatu* depletion, often precipitated by stress, faulty lifestyle, and improper diet. The Ayurvedic approach, therefore, emphasizes *Ahara*, *Vihara*, and *Aushadhi* to restore systemic balance and strengthen the reproductive tissues rather than providing symptomatic relief alone.

The present clinical trial compared a comprehensive *Vajikarana* protocol (Group A) with a simplified regimen (Group B). Group A demonstrated highly significant improvements in all major subjective parameters related to erectile strength, rigidity, desire, psychosexual confidence, and reduction in performance anxiety ($p < 0.0001$), indicating superior overall clinical recovery. Objective outcomes further validated these findings, with Group A showing a marked increase in total testosterone ($p < 0.0001$) and significant improvements in LH ($p = 0.0289$), demonstrating both endocrine and functional enhancement. Though FSH showed only moderate improvement and prolactin/TSH remained unchanged, the combined therapy produced meaningful physiological and psychological benefits.

Group B also showed significant improvements in subjective symptoms and strong enhancement in free testosterone ($p < 0.0001$) and LH ($p = 0.0040$), reflecting its hormonal influence. However, the degree of symptomatic relief and psychosexual improvement was comparatively lower than Group A, suggesting that hormonal enhancement alone is insufficient for complete restoration of erectile function.

Overall, the findings substantiate that the multimodal Ayurvedic regimen of Group A incorporating *Deepana-Pachana*, *Kostashodhana*, *Uttarabasti*, *Vajeekarana yoga* and *Shishna Lepa* offers superior efficacy by addressing both psychological and physiological components of *Klaibya*. This supports classical Ayurvedic principles that a holistic, multidimensional therapeutic approach yields more sustainable and comprehensive outcomes in the management of Erectile Dysfunction.

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